

WG6 Update

Scanning Lidar (SL) Recommended Practices (RP)

IEA Wind Task 52

Work Group 6

Activities and integration

- SL recommended practices role is to support IEC 61400-50-5
- Challenge of a technical specification being developed in parallel
- Scanning lidar is still seen as a new technology
- Our work has focused on evidence
- How do we do this?

Datathon 1

- Asked the question about sub-10-minute data availability
- Recovery Rate
- 10 participants
- Submitted 12 datasets

With thanks to :

F.IEE; F.IWES; DTU; Leice; Movelaser; SSE Renewables; Total Energies; Greenpower Investments; Oldbaum Services; AIST

Datathon 2: Uncertainty

- Asked the question about uncertainty assessment
- Again same participants
- We start to ask about LOS uncertainties
- A phase 2 part 2 is launched this month to further clarify
- Output: 1st stage uncertainty quantification seems

Datathon 3: Hard targetting

- A key component of scanning lidar is confidence in pointing accuracy
- We asked how this is done in the industry?
- We defined 5 methods:
 - Multi-target
 - Single target
 - Drone based targeting – Beam and drone acquisition methods
 - Sea surface levelling - RHI & PPI
 - System rotation

Output – we need to define better the methods and relative accuracies.

Uncertain approach to uncertainties

- To gain widespread commercial acceptance of Scanning Lidar we need an uncertainty framework
- Uncertainty is the key tool available to developers to justify measurement cost
- Can we simply adopt 50-3 (spoiler alert – No!)
- frameworks exist for :
 - Vertical profiling lidar (IEC61400-50-2)
 - Nacelle lidar (IEC 61400-50-3)
 - Floating lidar (IEC 61400-50-4)
- Can WG6 help IEA with uncertainties?

$$u_{FLS}^2 = u_{cla}^2 + u_{cal}^2 + u_{con}^2$$

From 50-3/4 to 50-5?

$$u_{SMC}^2 = u_{eoc}^2 + u_{RSD}^2 + u_{con}^2$$

Next steps – Phase 2 of datathon2

- Extends Datathon 2 – LOS uncertainties to final variable – Wind field reconstructed value
- Can be from single scanning lidar or multiple SL deployments
- Asks participants to use a standard industry model, but also invites other relevant models
- Aims to identify gaps

Datathon #2 – I

Assessment of SL uncertainties based on calibration of intermediate and final variables I

Context: I

Following datathon #1 on Data Availability, we intend to collect further experience and evidence with regard to the application of Doppler scanning lidar (SL) in this second datathon exercise focusing on SL uncertainties. The datathon is also aimed at informing IEC 61400-50-5 on the assessment of respective uncertainty and particularly the differentiation between uncertainties found for intermediate and final variables and more specifically line-of-sight (LOS) versus reconstructed horizontal wind speeds (v_{hor}) – as, e.g., also discussed in the recently published DNV/Vaisala white paper. I

Pre-requisites: I

- > SL dataset as for datathon #1 consisting of SL LOS data and reference met mast data, SL pointing at met mast anemometer in well-defined setup (to be detailed, see below) I
- > Either one SL, or 2 (or more) SL allowing for the reconstruction of horizontal wind speed I
- > Focus on 10-min data from SL and met mast anemometer I
- > Reference uncertainty of (projected) met mast anemometer data should be reported (if known) or estimated I
- > Sharing of results tables (as for typical calibration report) and overview plots I

Figure 2: Schematic of a line-of-sight (LOS) calibration setup I

Datathon #2 – Phase II I

This additional exercise builds on your Part 1 results (from “Phase I”). I

Use the LOS calibration results you have obtained to derive an uncertainty for v_{hor} . Present your results as bin-wise relative and/or absolute wind speed uncertainties, and detail the procedure you have applied. This could be an implementation of YADDUM (cf. [GitHub – e-WindLidar/YADDUM: Yet Another Dual-Doppler Uncertainty Model](#)) or any other model / framework. I

The calculations can be done for both DSL and single-SL data in principle. I

Remaining steps

- Collate and formulate
- Publish evidence
- Identify any remaining topics
- Start writing!

